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Performance assessment of PScyclone with regional configuration

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Contact details

Project Office: esiwace3@bsc.es

Website: www.esiwace.eu

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/esiwace>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/@esiwace880>

ESiWACE is on Zenodo, the Open Access repository for scientific results
<https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>

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Table of Contents

<i>Introduction</i>	5
<i>Model description</i>	5
Med24 Configuration	6
GLOB16 Configuration	7
<i>PSyclone settings</i>	9
Issues	15
<i>Performance Analysis</i>	15
Test configuration	15
Results	16
Conclusion	21
References	21

Introduction

Nowadays heterogeneous architectures of supercomputers have developed rapidly including multi-node parallelism and graphics processing units (GPUs), with the aim to build larger and even more energy efficient systems. On the other side climate models are more and more complex, computationally intensive and time-consuming. By harnessing the power of GPUs, climate researchers can accelerate simulations, enabling faster exploration of various climate scenarios. Then GPUs are becoming essential for accelerating scientific applications.

In this context, the activity related to Milestone M2.3 of the ESiWACE3 project aims to port two high-resolution CMCC configurations based on the NEMO Ocean model to GPUs using PSyclone. As better described in the next paragraphs, PSyclone is a source-to-source code generation and transformation system designed to improve performance portability and code maintainability for weather and climate codes written in Fortran. NEMO (Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean), one of the most widely used oceanic models in the climate community, is used by CMCC to build a regional configuration, MED24, and a global high-resolution configuration, named GLOB16, both described in the next sections. Finally, their performance evaluation on the hybrid nodes of the CMCC machine will be discussed.

Model description

The Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean (NEMO) is an ocean modelling platform widely used by a large user community for research activities and forecasting services in oceanography and science. It is developed and maintained by a European consortium of research institutions, including CNRS and Mercator-Ocean from France, NOC and the Met Office from the UK, and CMCC from Italy. The NEMO framework enables the creation of various configurations based on the NEMO-OCE ocean model, core of the infrastructure, which models ocean dynamics and thermodynamics using primitive equations. Additionally, two other modules can be added: NEMO-ICE, which computes the dynamics, rheology, and thermodynamics of sea ice, and NEMO-TOP-PISCES, which studies ocean tracer transport and biogeochemical processes.

The package also offers additional capabilities including the creation and use of nested regional grids at higher resolution via the bi-directional nesting package AGRIF; the possibility to generate parallel and/or asynchronous output using the efficient XIOS software; the ability to coupling interface to other climate system components based on OASIS; the integration of an external biogeochemical model; the providing of utility tools for pre- and post-processing data. NEMO is distributed with some “Reference Configurations” that cover the main NEMO features and capabilities and allow the user to easily set up their first application and help developers validate new developments. The global configurations use ORCA tripolar grid (Figure 1), which covers the entire oceanic domain without singularity points.

In fact, the grid formed by the meridians and parallels has two singularities: the North Pole and the South Pole. Near these two points, the size of the mesh tends to zero, complicating the use of modelling equations. To address the problem, the poles of the ORCA grids are repositioned on continents. Since the South Pole is located on the Antarctic continent, a modification of the standard grid is not required, while the North Pole, which is located in the Arctic Ocean, is replaced by two points one in North America and the other in Siberia. The ORCA grid is available in several horizontal resolutions ranging from approximately 2 degrees to 1/36 of a degree.

Figure 1. Tripolar grid used in global ORCA configuration.

The NEMO source code is written in Fortran 2008 and is parallelized through the MPI library using a domain decomposition method.

Since 2022, the NEMO system has been distributed through the NEMO GitLab Repository. The last stable version of the model is the 4.2.2 which was released in December 2023 and a new beta-5 version is actually under testing by the NEMO community.

Med24 Configuration

The Mediterranean Sea configuration is based on the operational Copernicus Marine Service Mediterranean analysis and forecasting physical system (MedFS).

The oceanic equations of motion are solved by NEMO, which is implemented in the Mediterranean Sea at a horizontal resolution of $1/24^\circ \times 1/24^\circ$ (approximately 3.5 km) and 141 unevenly spaced vertical levels (Clementi et al., 2017b), with a time step of 120 seconds. The model covers the entire Mediterranean Sea and extends into the Atlantic to better resolve the exchanges with the Atlantic Ocean at the Gibraltar Strait (Figure 2). The topography is created starting from the GEBCO 30 arc-second grid¹, filtered (using a Shapiro filter), and manually modified in critical areas such as islands along the Eastern Adriatic coasts, Gibraltar and Messina straits, and the Atlantic border.

The NEMO code solves the primitive equations using the time-splitting technique, explicitly resolving external gravity waves with a non-linear free surface formulation and time-varying vertical z-star coordinates. The advection scheme for active tracers (temperature and salinity) is a mixed up-stream/MUSCL (Monotonic Upwind Scheme for Conservation Laws). The vertical diffusion and viscosity terms are functions of the Richardson number, as parameterized by Pacanowsky and Philander (1981). The vertical background viscosity and diffusivity values are set to $1.2e-6 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ and $1.0e-7 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ respectively, while the horizontal bilaplacian eddy diffusivity and viscosity are set to $-1.2e8 \text{ m}^4/\text{s}$ and $-2.e8 \text{ m}^4/\text{s}$ respectively. A quadratic bottom

¹ http://www.gebco.net/data_and_products/gridded_bathymetry_data_gebco_30_second_grid/

ESiWACE3 Milestone M2.3

drag coefficient with a logarithmic formulation is used according to Maraldi et al. (2013), and the model uses vertical partial cells to fit the bottom depth shape.

The model is forced by momentum, water, and heat fluxes interactively computed by the MFS-bulk formulae (Pettenuzzo et al., 2010) using 6-hour temporal resolution and $1/10^\circ$ horizontal-resolution analysis fields from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), along with model-predicted surface temperatures (details of the air-sea physics are in Tonani et al., 2008). The water balance is computed as evaporation minus precipitation and runoff. Evaporation is derived from the latent heat flux, and precipitation is provided by ECMWF as daily averages. The runoff from 39 rivers is provided by monthly mean climatological data. The Dardanelles Strait is implemented as a lateral open boundary condition using the GLO-MFC daily Analysis and Forecast product and daily climatology derived from a Marmara Sea box model (Maderich et al., 2015). The tidal potential is computed across the domain for the 8 major constituents found in the Mediterranean Sea: M2, S2, N2, K2, K1, O1, P1, Q1. Additionally, tidal forcing is applied along the lateral boundaries in the Atlantic Ocean using tidal elevation estimated using the FES2014 (Carrere et al., 2016) tidal model, and tidal currents evaluated using TUGO (Toulouse Unstructured Grid Ocean model, ex-Mog2D; Lynch and Gray, 1979).

The model is nested in the Atlantic within the Copernicus Marine Global analysis and forecasting system daily dataset at a horizontal resolution of $1/12^\circ$ and 50 vertical levels (Copernicus Marine product GLOBAL_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_001_024). In particular, a Flather boundary condition is imposed for the barotropic velocities in the Atlantic (South, West, East), and a flow relaxation scheme is used for baroclinic velocities and tracers.

For a question of time, the first tests were done with a simpler configuration, which do not include tides nor rivers and as a first assumption, the model is not nested in the Atlantic and no boundary conditions are applied.

Figure 2: Model domain and bathymetry [m]

GLOB16 Configuration

GLOB16 is a global, eddy configuration of the ocean and sea ice system built on NEMO code version 4.2.2 (Madec et al., 2023). The model is based on its previous implementations documented in Iovino et al. (2016, 2023), it has been extensively upgraded following the code development since then, and used in a range of ocean studies (e.g. Treguier et al. 2023, Manral et al. 2023) and constitute the modelling core of the global ocean forecasting system at CMCC (<https://gofs.cmcc.it/>). GLOB16 makes use of a nonuniform tripolar grid with a $1/16^\circ$ horizontal resolution, which is 6.9 km at the equator, and increases poleward as the cosine of latitude (e.g. ~ 5.5 km at 40° , ~ 4 km at 60° and a minimum grid spacing of ~ 2 km around Victoria Island) - the grid has 5762×3963 grid points horizontally. Zonal and meridional scale factors are represented in Figure 3 (top row). The vertical coordinate system is based on fixed depth

ESiWACE3 Milestone M2.3

levels and consists of 98 vertical levels with a grid spacing increasing from approximately 1 m near the surface to 160 m in the deep ocean (Fig. 3 bottom row).

The ocean component is a finite difference, hydrostatic, primitive equation ocean general circulation model, with a linearized free sea surface, a free-slip lateral friction condition and an Arakawa C grid. Biharmonic viscosity and diffusivity schemes are used in the horizontal directions in the equations of momentums and tracers, respectively. Tracer advection uses a total variance dissipation (TVD) scheme (Zalesak, 1979). Vertical mixing is achieved using the turbulent kinetic energy (TKE) closure scheme (Blanke and Delecluse, 1993). Background coefficients of vertical diffusion and viscosity represent the vertical mixing induced by unresolved processes in the model. Vertical eddy mixing of both momentum and tracers is enhanced in case of static instability. The turbulent closure model does not apply any specific modification in ice-covered regions. Bottom friction is quadratic, and a diffusive bottom boundary layer scheme is included. All configurations use the EOS80 equation of the state of seawater (Fofonoff and Millard, 1983), with potential temperature and practical salinity as prognostic state variables.

Figure 3: Zonal (a) and meridional (b) scale factors (in km). Dashed contours start from 6 km in the equatorial region and decrease poleward with a 1km interval. c) Vertical level thickness (lower) as function of cumulative depth (in m).

The ocean component is coupled to the Sea Ice modelling Integrated Initiative (SI³, Vanconpenolle et al 2023), which was developed from the LIM3 model (Rousset et al. 2015) with some functionality merged from CICE (Hunke et al. 2015). Ocean and sea ice components share the same horizontal grid, ensuring consistency between these two interconnected systems. SI³ is fully embedded in the code and invoked from within the Surface Boundary

Code (SBC) module. The sea ice code is based on the Arctic Ice Dynamics Joint EXperiment (AIDJEX) framework, based on a 2+1D continuum approach and the ice thickness distribution framework, the conservation of horizontal momentum, elastic-viscous-plastic rheology (Hunke and Dukowicz, 1997), and energy-conserving halo-thermodynamics. In the horizontal direction, the model uses a curvilinear orthogonal grid. In the vertical direction, the model uses equally-spaced layers. In thickness space, our model uses 5 thickness categories with prescribed boundaries.

PSyclone settings

PSyclone is a source-to-source code generation and transformation system developed to support domain-specific languages (DSLs) for finite element, finite volume and finite difference codes. It is a tool designed to optimise, parallelize, and instrument High-Performance Computing (HPC) applications, specifically targeting Fortran code. It is especially useful in scientific computing, where performance and efficiency are critical.

PSyclone supports various parallel programming models and can generate code for different HPC platforms. This includes shared-memory parallelism (using OpenMP), distributed-memory parallelism (using MPI), and accelerator-based parallelism (using OpenACC). This multi-platform support helps ensure that applications can be efficiently executed on a wide range of hardware configurations.

PSyclone operates as a source-to-source compiler, meaning it takes Fortran source code as input, applies various transformations to improve performance, and then generates optimised Fortran code as output.

PSyclone transformations are user-provided scripts allowing to apply optimizations and parallelization strategies, such as choosing between OpenMP and OpenACC for parallel execution, to the code. By encapsulating performance and portability decisions in scripts, PSyclone separates the scientific implementation of an application from its optimization and parallelization strategies. This allows developers to focus on the scientific aspects while optimization experts can independently enhance performance.

The transformations are designed to act on the Parallelisation System (PSy) layer. It is at the heart of PSyclone and its primary role is to provide node-based parallel performance for the target architecture. A PSyIR (PSyclone Internal Representation) tree can be built from scratch in Python or by processing existing source code with a frontend.

PSyclone NEMO API is designed to treat the NEMO source code as if it were a manually written PSy layer with all kernels in-lined. This approach leverages on the NEMO Coding Conventions. In the case of NEMO, PSyclone parses the existing Fortran and creates a higher-level representation of it, the PSyIR, that is where the transformations are applied.

The PSy layer can be optimised for a particular hardware architecture, such as multi-core, many-core, GPGPUs, or some combination thereof with no change to the scientific code.

The final code generated by PSyclone is created by passing the PSyIR tree to the NEMO Fortran ‘backends’ (Figure 4). This approach therefore offers the potential for portable performance.

Figure 4. PSyclone as source-to-source compiler in NEMO environment

PSyclone is available on the Python Package Index (PyPI) and is hosted on GitHub. The latest release is 2.5.0 and the latest stable version is on the master branch.

Various aspects of PSyclone are configured through a configuration file, `psyclone.cfg`. At execution-time, the user can specify a custom configuration file to be used by specifying the path to the configuration file to use via the `PSYCLONE_CONFIG` environment variable.

The configuration file is read by the Python `ConfigParser` class and has to be formatted accordingly. It currently is composed of a `DEFAULT` section, applicable to all APIs supported by PSyclone, and an optional API specific section. The specific API for NEMO code includes a `mapping-TYPE` entry, declaring a mapping for a certain loop level, specified as `TYPE`.

Additionally an `index-order` entry is present to specify the order in which loops are created when converting an implicit loop to an explicit loop.

The example in Figure 5 shows the NEMO section of a PSyclone configuration file. In the `mapping-TYPE` entry each value has three `key:value` pairs. A value can be empty if it is not required or not known, but the key must still be specified. The required keys are `var`, the variable name that indicates the loop level, `start`, the first loop iteration, and `stop`, the last loop iteration. The values in `index-order` have corresponding mapping entries, e.g. `mapping-lon`, `mapping-lat`, etc.

```
mapping-lon = var: ji, start: 1, stop: jpi
mapping-lat = var: jj, start: 1, stop: jpj
mapping-levels = var: jk, start: 1, stop: jpk
mapping-tracers = var: jt, start: 1, stop:
mapping-unknown = var: , start: 1, stop:

index-order = lon, lat, levels, tracers
```

Figure 5. Example of PSyclone configuration file for NEMO

According to this convention, a NEMO loop specifying `DO JI=...` will be assigned to the type `'lon'` by PSyclone, because the loop uses the variable name specified in the configuration file for a loop of type `'lon'`.

The entry `mapping-unknown` has an empty value for the key `'var'` meaning that the type `'unknown'` will be used for any loop that cannot be mapped using any of the other variable names in the configuration file.

The use of PSyclone to transform the source code from the NEMO ocean model can be easily tested through the examples provided in the GitHub repository. They show how the `psyclone` command, that is the simplest way to run PSyclone, can be used to parallelise all loops over levels in a tracer-advection and a tracer-diffusion NEMO routines, using OpenMP and OpenACC transformations, for the targeting on CPUs and GPUs.

ESiWACE3 Milestone M2.3

Some other scripts are also provided that aid the use of PSyclone with the full NEMO model. These are, basically, a wrapper script, named `process_nemo.py`, that allows a user to control which source files are transformed, which only have profiling instrumentation added and which are ignored altogether, and some transformations scripts - `acc_kernels_trans.py`, `omp_gpu_trans.py`, `acc_loops_trans.py` and `omp_cpu_trans.py` - which add the optimizations to the regions of the code being processed.

These scripts provided the starting point for the integration of PSyclone in the NEMO framework. In fact, from the 5.0-beta release the PSyclone processing step has been included into the NEMO build system, based on the build sub-system of the Flexible Configuration Management system, as an additional complete build process that comprises regular source-code pre-processing followed by a modified Fortran compilation stage that performs PSyclone processing, resulting in "object" files that are actually PSyclone-processed source code files instead of actual object files.

The integration of PSyclone into the NEMO build system aims to manage transformations across the whole set of source code files, usually the entire NEMO source code, with few exceptions. This integration includes dependency analysis to streamline recompilation during development and after applying source-code patches, and ensures seamless integration into multi-stage build processes that already involve source-to-source transformations of the NEMO source code (e.g., AGRIF). Anyway, at this time only the passthrough testing (where code is processed by PSyclone but not transformed) of all SETTE configurations with the latest release version of PSyclone is successful has been tested without changes to the code/scripts. To allow the PSyclone integration the `makenemo` script has been revised and extended with the introduction of a new option `-p` followed by the name of the PSyclone transformation to be enabled.

In the following example the PSyclone transformation `acc_kernel_trans` for the addition of OpenACC `kernels` directives across a large portion of the NEMO source code has been enabled. The transformation script has been taken from the PSyclone repository and added to the directory `sct/` of the NEMO framework, in order to provide a transformation option selectable via option `-p` of `makenemo`.

```
./makenemo -m auto-psyclone -n GYRE_tr_PSyclone -r GYRE_PISCES -p  
acc_kernels_trans del_key "key_top key_xios"
```

Figure 6. NEMO compilation with PSyclone support

The new option triggers the call to `mk/sct_psyclone.sh` script, applying PSyclone to the NEMO source code. It is a wrapper file allowing to control the PSyclone processing steps and, eventually, can be modified by adding the files that fail to compile to the list of files to exclude from PSyclone compilation.

Definitely, with PSyclone processing, the build system processes the NEMO source code in three stages (or with AGRIF in four stages): CPP preprocessing, PSyclone processing, and the actual compilation.

Although the NEMO framework is not still fully compliant with PSyclone transformation (only the `-p` 'passthrough' option is actually working on the whole set of reference configurations), the main goal of this work is to apply the PSyclone chain using `acc_kernel_trans` transformation to the global and regional CMCC configurations described before, in order to introduce the `acc kernel` directives in NEMO code, allowing the targeting on the NVIDIA GPUs of CMCC machine, and evaluate the performance.

ESiWACE3 Milestone M2.3

When this work began the PSyclone integration in the NEMO framework was just starting, so many issues have been addressed to get a configuration running on GPU.

The first attempts to have a working configuration have been made with the PSyclone v2.3.1 and a NEMO version based on the main after v4.2.1.

The first challenge was the setup of a working NVIDIA environment. On the CMCC machine the module <NVIDIA HPC SDK Version 22.3>, a suite of NVIDIA compilers and libraries, is installed and can be easily loaded. Anyway the HDF5 and NetCFD library, needed to build and run NEMO, are provided only with the INTEL compiler on the system and not suitable to work with the NVIDIA compiler. Therefore, a user installation of the libraries built using the NVIDIA compiler was necessary.

Nevertheless the job continued to fail during the execution phase due to a 'PMIX ERROR: UNREACHABLE in file ../../../../../../../opal/mca/pmix/pmix3x/pmix/src/server/pmix_server.c at line 2198', causing an MPI_ABORT that killed all MPI processes in the communicator.

After some investigations it was discovered the error derived from OpenMPI installation in NVIDIA SDK package. In particular OpenMPI configure should have used external PMIx, libevent and hwloc libraries to ensure proper operation.

In order to solve the issue hwloc and libevent libraries have been installed. Then the PMIx library has been configured and built against the new libevent and the hwloc packages. Finally, OpenMPI compiler has been configured and built, specifying the location of the PMIx, libevent, and hwloc packages and adding a directive to directly use PMIx installation of these libraries. The working environment finally used for the experiments is shown in Figure 7, where:

- /work/cmcc/fm27215/gpu_omp_env_new/shared/lib directory contains hwloc, libevent and PMIX libraries
- /work/cmcc/fm27215/shared/src/nvhpc-ompi-lib-new/lib directory includes HDF5, NetCDF-C and NetCDF-F
- /work/cmcc/fm27215/gpu_omp_env_new/compiler/bin directory includes the Open MPI compiler

```
#bin/bash

module purge
module load intel-2021.6.0/perl-xml-parser/2.44-27mmx
module load intel-2021.6.0/perl/5.36.0-jj4hw
module load gcc-12.2.0/12.2.0
module load nvhpc-22.3-nompi/22.3
export PATH=/work/cmcc/fm27215/gpu_omp_env_new/compiler/bin:$PATH
export CPATH=/work/cmcc/fm27215/gpu_omp_env_new/compiler/include:$CPATH
export OMPI_HOME=/work/cmcc/fm27215/gpu_omp_env_new/compiler
export MPI_HOME=/work/cmcc/fm27215/gpu_omp_env_new/compiler
export OPAL_PREFIX=/work/cmcc/fm27215/gpu_omp_env_new/compiler
export LD_LIBRARY_PATH=/work/cmcc/fm27215/shared/src/nvhpc-ompi-lib-new/lib:$LD_LIBRARY_PATH
export
export LD_LIBRARY_PATH=/work/cmcc/fm27215/gpu_omp_env_new/shared/lib:$LD_LIBRARY_PATH
export
export LD_LIBRARY_PATH=/work/cmcc/fm27215/gpu_omp_env_new/compiler/lib:$LD_LIBRARY_PATH
```

Figure 7. Nvidia environment built for the tests

Then the new compiler and libraries have been used to build the architecture file to be specified in the ./makenemo command. For this purpose the build_arch-auto.sh script, a tool provided with NEMO, that facilitates the generation of the architecture configuration file has

ESiWACE3 Milestone M2.3

been used. It allows you to automatically determine some architecture-specific configuration settings and to generate a new architecture file at `arch-auto.fcm`. To be able to use PScyclone the NEMO configuration file has to include the `"%PSYCLONE_HOME"` variable. It needs to be set in the PScyclone installation directory. Figure 8 shows the generated arch-file for the CMCC JUNO supercomputer equipped with 20 GPU Nvidia A100. Note the use of PGI's 'managed memory' option to deal with data movement between CPU/GPU.

```
# Mon Nov 6 13:31:34 CET 2023
#
%NCDF_C_PREFIX          /work/cmcc/fm27215/shared/src/nvhpc-mpi-lib-new
%NCDF_F_PREFIX          /work/cmcc/fm27215/shared/src/nvhpc-mpi-lib-new
%HDF5_PREFIX            /work/cmcc/fm27215/shared/src/nvhpc-mpi-lib-new

%PSYCLONE_HOME          /users_home/cmcc/fm27215/.local

%ATOMIC_PREFIX          /juno/opt/gcc/12.2.0
%NCDF_INC                -I%NCDF_F_PREFIX/include -I%NCDF_C_PREFIX/include -
I%ATOMIC_PREFIX/include
%NCDF_LIB                -L%NCDF_F_PREFIX/lib -lnetcdf -L%NCDF_C_PREFIX/lib -
lnetcdf -L%HDF5_PREFIX/lib -lhdf5_hl -lhdf5 -lhdf5_fortran -lz -lm -
L%ATOMIC_PREFIX/lib64 -latomic

%CPP                     cpp -Dkey_nosignedzero
%CPPFLAGS                -Dkey_nosignedzero
%FC                       mpifort
%FCFLAGS                 -i4 -r8 -O3 -Minfo -Mneginfo -acc=gpu -fpic -fortranlibs -
ta=tesla:managed
%FFLAGS                  %FCFLAGS
%LD                       %FC
%LDFLAGS                 -lstc++ -lz -lgpfs -acc=gpu -ta=tesla:managed
%FPPFLAGS                -P -traditional
%AR                       ar
%ARFLAGS                 rs
%MK                       make
%USER_INC                %NCDF_INC
%USER_LIB                %NCDF_LIB
```

Figure 8. *arch-auto* file automatically generated

As a first attempt, before moving on to more complex configurations, the NEMO GYRE configuration has been used as a test case.

To simplify the build process the `sct/psct-acc_kernels_trans.py` file has been edited slightly by changing `PROFILE_NONACC` value from `'True.'` to `'False.'`, and by commenting the `'from utils import add_profiling'` statement to avoid a `fcm_internal` compile failure in `sbcice_cice.f90` file.

Unfortunately the Fortran compiler from the NVIDIA HPC SDK was not among the supported compilers for NEMO 'main' version used at the beginning, and a few source-code adjustments were required to avoid compilation failures. The issues were the use of variables of type `REAL(KIND=2*wp)` in source-code file `'src/OCE/IOM/prtctl.F90'`, and the use of the `'ISNAN'` intrinsic in `'src/OCE/stpctl.F90'`. The former was avoided by reducing the precision of the `'sn_cfctl%l_prtctl'` output to `'REAL(KIND=wp)'` (i.e. replacing `'2*wp'` by `'wp'` throughout `'src/OCE/IOM/prtctl.F90'`), and the latter by replacing `'ISNAN'` by `'ieee_is_nan'` (which requires `'USE, INTRINSIC :: ieee_arithmetic, ONLY : ieee_is_nan'`).

Finally in order to avoid further errors, the PScyclone processing has been explicitly disabled for some files that fail to compile by adding their name to the list of `sct_pscyclone.sh` exclusions (e.g. `[["${FILENAME}" == 'obs_types.f90']] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'`) until the

compilation is successful. Figure 9 contains the list of files that was needed to exclude to compile GYRE, MED24 and GLOB16 configurations using PScyclone v2.5.0.

```

if [ ${PSYCLONE_VERSION} == "2.5.0" ]; then
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'timing.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'lbclnk.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'prtctl.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'stopar.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'stopts.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'fldread.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'bdyini.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'ldfslp.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'domtile.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'zdfgls.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'icbdia.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'sbcssr.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'dtatsd.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'obs_grid.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'obs_surf_def.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'obs_profiles_def.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'obs_avergh2d.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'obs_types.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'obs_read_prof.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'obs_read_surf.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'sbcblk_algo_andreas.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'sbcblk_algo_coare3p0.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'sbcblk_algo_coare3p6.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'sbcblk_algo_ncar.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'sbcblk_algo_ice_an05.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'sbcblk_algo_ice_lg15.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'sbcblk_algo_ice_lul2.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'sbcblk_algo_mfs.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'icedyn_rhg_evp.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'icedyn_adv_umx.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'icbutl.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'diaar5.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'diadct.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'bdydyn2d.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'dynhpg.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'traadv_mus.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'traadv_qck.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'traadv_ubs.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'trabbl.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'zdfmfc.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'fldread_ECMWF.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'bdyice.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'lbcnfd.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'icectl.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'icedyn_adv.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'icedyn_rhg_vp.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'icedyn.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'bdydt.a.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'trdra.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'sbcblk.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'bdydyn2d.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'bdydyn3d.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'bdytra.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'iom.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'
[[ "${FILENAME}" == 'zdfdrg.f90' ]] && ACTION='EXCLUDE'

```

Figure 9. List of files excluded from PScyclone processing in `sct_pscyclone.sh` script

Issues

The described settings allow the Nvidia compiler to successfully compile the GYRE, MED24 and GLOB16 configurations using PSyclone v2.5.0. and NEMO main after v4.2.2 release on the JUNO CMCC supercomputer. Since NEMO releases v4.2.2 many advancements have been made for the PSyclone integration and the Nvidia compiler compatibility. Therefore the changes to the NEMO source code were no longer needed.

Regarding the MED24, a simplified version of the configuration, excluding tides and rivers, was used for the initial tests. This was due to difficulties in porting the full configuration to the NEMO main or 5.0-beta release. Additionally, during execution, issues arose after reading the boundary-related files, which appeared to have incorrect dimensions and data sizes, resulting in a segmentation fault error. The error, probably related to the Nvidia compiler / environment, has been temporarily bypassed, disabling the unstructured open boundaries by namelist in this phase.

Issues are arising during the execution phase of the GLOB16 configuration, too. In particular, during the ice shelf initialisation, the job remains hanging without errors. Other similar problems were previously fixed by adding the name of the routine concerning the issue to the ACC_IGNORE list in psct-acc_kernels_trans.py PSyclone transformation script. It represents the list of routines PSyclone does not attempt to add any OpenACC directive (because it breaks with the Nvidia compiler or because it just isn't worth it).

Anyway this trick is not working in the ice shelf initialization case. So for now the performance analysis has been carried out on the GYRE configuration using a resolution similar to the GLOB16 case.

Performance Analysis

Test configuration

In this section the performance tests executed on the target machine, the CMCC JUNO supercomputer are reported. The JUNO machine is equipped with 160 Compute nodes type Lenovo SD630 v2 and 10 Hybrid nodes type (CPU+GPU) Lenovo SR670 v2. The Compute nodes are equipped with 72 Intel Xeon P. 8360 processors and 512 GB RAM. Each hybrid node is composed of 72 Intel Xeon P. 8360Y processors and 2 GPU NVIDIA A100 40GB. The main memory per node is 1024 GB. The machine uses the Spectrum LSF v. 10.2 as the batch queueing system.

The Nvidia environment used during the compilation step, and described in Figure 7, has been used in the tests execution phase. Figure 10 shows an example of the submission script used for the test. `g_devel` is one of the GPU submission queues available on the JUNO machine. The GPU requirements for the job can be specified together with the `-gpu` option. By default, the number is per host. The GPU mode when the job is running can be either shared or exclusive process. The default mode on CMCC machine is exclusive process. Anyway, when the multi-node job is submitted the shared mode is needed in order the job doesn't get stalled. As can be seen in the reported results, if on the one hand this selection allows the use of a greater number of GPUs, on the other significantly it seems to degrade the execution time.

```
#BSUB -q g_devel
#BSUB -n 2
#BSUB -J MED24_GPU
#BSUB -P 0603
#BSUB -o poe.stdout.%J
#BSUB -e poe.stderr.%J
#BSUB -R "span[ptile=2]"
#BSUB -gpu "num=2"
#BSUB -x

source load_gpu_env
mpirun -n 2 ./nemo.exe
```

Figure 10. Example of submission script used for the tests on GPUs

Results

A 6-hour simulation period was utilised for the MED24 configuration tests, corresponding to 180 time steps, having each single step a duration of 120 seconds. The writing of the full *timing.output* file has been activated from the namelist in order to obtain more detailed statistics.

Each experiment has been conducted using an increasing number of resources (CPUs or GPUs).

Next table shows the elapsed time - extracted by *timing.output* file (s) - detected running the MED24 configuration on the CPUs and GPUs nodes. The used criteria was to compare the test performed on 1 GPU with the same test running on 1 CPU, i.e. 36 cores. In a similar way the elapsed time of the run on 72 cores of Intel Xeon P. has been compared with the time resulting by the use of 2 NVIDIA A100 GPUs, and so on.

MED24	Elapsed time (s) using Intel Xeon P. 8360	Elapsed time (s) using NVIDIA A100
1 core	43.806	
2 cores	21.717	
4 cores	13.568	
8 cores	5.494	
36 cores (1 CPU) / 1 GPU	1.157	3.875
72 cores (2 CPU) / 2 GPU	614	2.163
144 cores (4 CPU) / 4 GPU	296	3.853
288 cores (8 CPU) / 8 GPU	153	4.113

Table 1. Elapsed times of the MED24 configuration running on CPUs and GPUs

Each test ended successfully producing the expected NEMO output files (run.stat, ocean.ooutput, NetCDF restart and output files).

ESiWACE3 Milestone M2.3

The following figures show the elapsed time for each time step of the experiments using 1 CPU, i.e. 36 cores, in the first plot (Figure 11) and 1 GPU in the second one (Figure 12). They enable highlighting the timing differences across various timesteps. As can be noted, the execution on GPU increases by a factor of 10 on average the time for each iteration.

Figure 11. Timing step from t1 to t180 on 1 CPU (36 cores)

Figure 12. Timing step from t1 to t180 on 1 GPU

The times in the previous table have been then used to produce the graphic in Figure 13, showing the MED24 scalability on CPUs and GPUs. Using 1 CPU the time is ~70% faster than the elapsed time on 1 GPU. The same gain is registered by using 2 CPUs versus 2 GPUs. With a larger number of GPUs the time even increases. The problems in performance scalability is probably due to the shared memory between GPUs. Unfortunately this mode submission can not be avoided in order the job doesn't get stalled. Anyway this problem needs to be further investigated.

Figure 13. Scalability of the MED24 configuration on CPUs and GPUs

Finally, the histograms of the MED24 most computationally intensive routines are reported in Figure 14. The first bar represents the elapsed time of the routine in execution on 1 CPU, the second one denotes the execution time using 1 GPU while in the third one both the GPUs of the hybrid node are used. No advantage is found in using GPUs.

Figure 14. Time comparison of the most computationally intensive MED24 routines running on 1 CPU, 1 GPU and 2 GPUs, respectively

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The same tests have been performed for the GYRE 50 configuration. A global domain of 1502 x 1002 x 31 grid points has been used for the test with a simulation length of 6 hours, corresponding to 180 time steps, having set up the single time step duration to 200s to simulate as much as possible the GLOB16 configuration. Higher resolution choices result in additional issues during the execution phase on GPUs that need to be further investigated.

Next table shows the elapsed time detected running the GYRE configuration on the CPUs and GPUs nodes. The same approach described before has been taken for this set of tests.

GYRE50	Elapsed time (s) using Intel Xeon P. 8360	Elapsed time (s) using NVIDIA A100
1 core	2.111	
2 cores	928	
4 cores	579	
8 cores	294	
36 cores (1 CPU) / 1 GPU	101	1.306
72 cores (2 CPU) / 2 GPU	88	724
144 cores (4 CPU) / 4 GPU	47	1.174
288 cores (8 CPU) / 8 GPU	24	1.742

Table 2. Elapsed times of the GYRE50 configuration running on CPUs and GPUs

The times in the previous table have been then used to produce the graphic in Figure 15, showing the GYRE 50 scalability on CPUs and GPUs. Using 1 GPU the time decreases by a factor of 10 than the elapsed time on 1 CPU. As before, with a larger number of GPUs the worsening even increases probably due to the shared memory between GPUs.

Finally, for the GYRE 50 configuration, too, the histograms of the most computationally intensive routines are reported in Figure 16. As before, the first bar represents the elapsed time of the routine in execution on 1 CPU, the second one denotes the execution time using 1 GPU while in the third one both the GPUs of the hybrid node are used. Also in this case the use of GPU breaks the performance in all the analysed routines.

Figure 15. Scalability of the GYRE50 configuration on CPUs and GPUs

Figure 16. Time comparison of the most computationally intensive GYRE50 routines running on 1 CPU, 1 GPU and 2 GPUs, respectively

Conclusion

The experiments demonstrated that the use of PSyclone to obtain a GPU-ready version of the code is not trivial, especially for non standard configurations, and it requires a deeper fine tuning activity. At the moment several modules of NEMO are still not supported by PSyclone `acc_kernel` transformation. However, for the next steps the aim is to manually modify the generated code to achieve better performance and support the PSyclone developers to implement such transformations in the next version of PSyclone.

References

Madec, G. and the NEMO System Team. NEMO Ocean Engine. NEMO Ocean Engine Reference Manual. [Online] 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8167700>.

The XIOS official website. [Online] <https://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/ioserver>.

The Oasis official website. [Online] <https://oasis.cerfacs.fr/en/home/>.

PSyclone: Domain-specific compiler and code transformation system for Finite Volume/Difference/Element Earth-system models in Fortran, <https://github.com/stfc/PSyclone>

Blanke, B. and Delecluse, P.: Variability of the tropical Atlantic Ocean simulated by a general circulation model with two different mixed layer physics, *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, 23, 1363–1388, 1993.

Fofonoff, N. P. and Millard Jr., R. C.: Algorithms for the computation of fundamental properties of seawater. Paris, France, UNESCO, UNESCO Technical Papers in Marine Sciences, 44, 53 pp., <https://doi.org/10.25607/OBP-1450>, 1983.

Hunke, E. C., & Dukowicz, J. K. (1997). An elastic-viscous-plastic model for sea ice dynamics. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 27, 1849–1867.

Hunke, E. C., Lipscomb, W. H., Turner, A. K., Jeffery, N., and Elliott, S. (2015). CICE: The Los Alamos Sea Ice Model Documentation and Software User's Manual Version 5.1. LA-CC-06–012. Los Alamos, NM: Los Alamos National Laboratory. Available online at: <http://www.ccpo.odu.edu/~klinck/Reprints/PDF/cicedoc2015.pdf> (accessed March 17, 2015).

Iovino, D., Masina, S., Storto, A., Cipollone, A., and Stepanov, V. N.: A $1/16^\circ$ eddy simulation of the global NEMO sea-ice–ocean system, *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 9, 2665–2684, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-9-2665-2016>, 2016.

Iovino, D., Fogli, P. G., and Masina, S.: Evaluation of the CMCC global eddy ocean model for the Ocean Model Intercomparison Project (OMIP2), *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 16, 6127–6159, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-16-6127-2023>, 2023.

Madec, G. and the NEMO System Team (2023). NEMO Ocean Engine Reference Manual. In *Scientific Notes of IPSL Climate Modelling Center* (v4.2.1, Number 27). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8167700>

ESiWACE3 Milestone M2.3

Manral, D., Iovino, D., Jaillon, O., Masina, S., Sarmiento, H., Iudicone, D., & Van Sebille, E. (2023). Computing marine plankton connectivity under thermal constraints. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 10, 1066050. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2023.1066050>

Rousset, C., Vancoppenolle, M., Madec, G., Fichefet, T., Flavoni, S., Barthélemy, A., Benshila, R., Chanut, J., Levy, C., Masson, S., and Vivier, F.: The Louvain-La-Neuve sea ice model LIM3.6: global and regional capabilities, *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 8, 2991–3005, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-8-2991-2015>, 2015.

Treguier, A. M., de Boyer Montégut, C., Bozec, A., Chassignet, E. P., Fox-Kemper, B., McC. Hogg, A., Iovino, D., Kiss, A. E., Le Sommer, J., Li, Y., Lin, P., Lique, C., Liu, H., Serazin, G., Sidorenko, D., Wang, Q., Xu, X., and Yeager, S.: The mixed-layer depth in the Ocean Model Intercomparison Project (OMIP): impact of resolving mesoscale eddies, *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 16, 3849–3872, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-16-3849-2023>, 2023

Vancoppenolle, M., Rousset, C., Blockley, E., Aksenov, Y., Feltham, D., Fichefet, T., Garric, G., Guémas, V., Iovino, D., Keeley, S., Madec, G., Massonnet, F., Ridley, J., Schroeder, D., & Tietsche, S. (2023). SI3, the NEMO Sea Ice Engine (4.2release_doc1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7534900>

Zalesak, S. T.: Fully multidimensional flux corrected transport for fluids, *J. Comput. Phys.*, 31, 335–362, 1979.